

***PROBLEMS OF HANDLOOM WEAVERS IN ANDHRA
PRADESH: A SPECIAL REFERENCE TO RAYALASEEMA
REGION***

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ABSTRACT

The handloom sector is one of the largest unorganized economic activities and it constitutes an integral part of the rural and semi-rural livelihood. The handloom industry weavers are faced many problems in day-to-day transaction. This study has been made an attempt to identify the problems faced by the handloom weavers in Rayalaseema region, A.P and to give the suitable suggestions to improve the handloom industry. The study has been carried out in three districts viz., Chittoor, Annamayya and Tirupati in Rayalaseema region of Andhra Pradesh. The study has been adopted a stratified sampling design for collection of data. The total sample comprises of 360 of the weaver's households. It is found that majority of the 342 sample respondent handloom weavers (95.00 per cent) were facing the financial problems and 18 sample respondent handloom weavers (5.00 per cent) were not facing financial problems in Rayalaseema region. It is suggested that the Government of India has been introduced several welfare schemes to handloom weavers but, the benefits are not reached to appropriate person various steps to be taken for attractive benefits. It is concluded that the handloom weavers of Rayalaseema region in Andhra Pradesh various problems are faced in respect of production, finance, health and labour problems. The handloom weavers cannot sell their products directly to the consumers. Today's no modern marketing techniques especially e- marketing, are not adopted by them.

Keywords: Handloom sector, Financial Problems, Production Problems, Health Problems, Labour Problems

INTRODUCTION

The handloom weaving industry plays a very imperative role in the India's economy. In case of employment, it is the second largest sector next only to agriculture. The Handloom Sector is one of the largest unorganized economic activities of India and it constitutes an integral part of the rural and semi-rural livelihood engaging over 35 lakh persons. The sector engages over 25 lakh female weavers and allied workers which makes it an important source of economic empowerment of women. Handloom weaving constitutes one of the richest and most vibrant aspects of the Indian cultural heritage. The sector has advantage of being less capital intensive, minimal use of power, being eco-friendly, flexibility of small production, openness to innovations and adaptability to market requirements. Because of the uniqueness and exclusivity of designs, capability to produce small batch sizes and being ecofriendly fabric, handloom products are in high demand in the international and the domestic market and retailers with discerning clientele looking for reliable source of authentic handloom products on regular basis.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Gangaraju.V. (2020) in his article entitled "The Problems and Perspectives of Handloom Weavers (A Study in Guntur District of Andhra Pradesh)", this article aimed at to know the income, expenditure pattern of the sample respondents, to analyze the living pattern conditions of the weavers and to study the health issues of the weavers. The study was adopted a stratified purposive sampling design for collection of data. The total sample comprises of 250 of the weavers households. It is found that most of the respondents are struggling with multiple health issues especially Sight, Hernia, Orthopedic and B.P, Piles are major health problems. Weaving Co-operative Societies are very poor performance importantly fake societies enjoying the fruits. It is suggested that Government should encourage the independent weavers with special interest. Government should take necessary measures to reorganize the defunct co-operative societies and take necessary actions on them. There is a need for inclusive legislation on occupational health and safety for the handloom sector.

Divya C V, Gopika C V & Krishna M (2020), in their article entitled "Financial Problems Faced by Handloom Weavers in Chendamangalam Co-operative Society", the study is focused on the various financial problems faced by the handloom weavers in Chendamangalam handloom co-operative society as well as the schemes are available from the government. It is found that majority of the handloom weavers who involve in the weaving were women between

the age group of 40-50 years and having experience of more than 4 years. The present survey was very meagre which is insufficient to meet their day-to-day activities. It is concluded that wage hike is the need of the hour and the wages should be provided to them without any delay. The immediate intervention of the Government is inevitable for the survival of these handloom weavers.

Sangeetha.S. & Adaikala Charles S. (2019) in their article entitled “A Study on Problems and Prospective of Handloom Weavers in selected areas of Thanjavur District, Tamilnadu”, this paper has analysed that to study the present situation of handloom sector and to examine the problems faced by handloom weavers. The study is based on primary data collected from 120 respondents by using a structured questionnaire and through personal interview method. It is suggested that the government has to implement skill development programs, create awareness on technological changes that are suitable for the handloom industry, financial support for up gradation of technology, providing credit facilities, development of marketing facilities, strategies for ensuring confidence in youth for taking handloom as a profession. It is concluded that to enable the sector to realize full potential, the bottlenecks which hinder the development must be removed. Both the Central and State Governments should recognize the role of handlooms in achieving sustainable development.

Jayachandra, K. and Subramanyam Naidu, L. (2018) study focused on the handloom weaver’s co-operative societies in Chittoor district-a case study highlighted the importance of co-operative societies and its benefits to the weaving community. The study showed how the weaving communities have become workless. It is also highlighted the functioning of the co-operative societies. It is found that how co-operative societies are not active in the recent times due to various reasons. It is concluded that the government must take care and provide the essential support to rejuvenate the industry.

Srinivasa Rao. D & Sreedhar. N (2017) in their study, “Problems of Handloom Weavers in Andhra Pradesh: A study of Krishna District”, the objectives of this study are to find out the problems of handloom weavers in Krishna District and make a focus on the welfare programme conducted by state and central Government. The primary data was collected from 120 respondents by using a structured questionnaire and through personal interview method. It is found that majority of the 93 respondents (77.50%) weavers are facing financial problems and the lowest number 27(22.50%) respondents are not facing financial problems. It is suggested that the malpractices of the master weavers should be controlled and there must be a fair propaganda relating to the use of handloom cloth to increase the sales. It is concluded that to enhance the scope of weaving activity, measures should also be taken to provide raw materials,

finance, marketing facilities and other requirements. Both the central and state governments should recognize the role of handlooms in achieving sustainable development.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following objectives of the present study are:

- To analyse the problems faced by the handloom weavers in Rayalaseema region, A.P and
- To give the suitable suggestions to improve the handloom industry in Rayalaseema region, A.P.

HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses are formulated on the basis of the set of objectives for the present study:

- There is no significant relationship between the production problems of sample respondent handloom weavers of Annamayya, Chittoor and Tirupati districts in Rayalaseema region.
- There is no significant relationship between the financial problems of sample respondent handloom weavers of Annamayya, Chittoor and Tirupati districts in Rayalaseema region.
- There is no significant relationship between the health problems of sample respondent handloom weavers of Annamayya, Chittoor and Tirupati districts in Rayalaseema region.
- There is no significant relationship between the labour problems of sample respondent handloom weavers of Annamayya, Chittoor and Tirupati districts in Rayalaseema region.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

SAMPLE DESIGN

The study has been carried out in three districts viz., Chittoor, Annamayya and Tirupati in Rayalaseema region of Andhra Pradesh. The total population number 7294 consisting of Annamayya district (4897), Chittoor district (1195) and Tirupati district (1104) are having handloom weavers' population who are involved in weaving. The primary data collections 5 per cent of total handloom weavers are taken as sample. The total sample comprises of 360 of the weaver's households. The sample respondent handloom weaver consisting of Annamayya district (245), Chittoor district (60) and Tirupati district (55) are selected simple random sampling was adopted for the present study.

COLLECTION OF DATA

Data was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data was collected through a well-structured questionnaire and through personal interview method. The secondary data was collected from books, journals, magazines, internet and daily newspapers.

PERIOD OF THE STUDY

The primary data has been collected from the sample respondent handloom weavers for the year 2023-24.

TOOLS OF DATA ANALYSIS

The data collected from the various sources have been analyzed with the help of appropriate statistical tools and relevant mathematical devices like average, percentages, Chi-Square test etc.

PRODUCTION PROBLEMS

Handloom weavers are facing production problems are scarcity of yarn, raw material problems, design improvement, lack of technology development, enhancement of value, technology& mechanization patenting designs/varieties and working hours. The sample respondent handloom weavers whether they are facing production problems or not in Rayalaseema region is presented in table-1 hereunder;

Table 1: Sample respondent handloom weavers whether they are facing production problems or not in Rayalaseema Region

Sample respondent handloom weavers	Name of the District			
	Annamayya	Chittoor	Tirupati	Total
Yes	236(74.92) (96.33)	38(12.06) (63.33)	41(13.02) (74.55)	315(100) (87.50)
No	09 (20.00) (3.67)	22 (48.89) (36.67)	14 (31.11) (25.45)	45 (100) (12.50)
Total	245 (68.06) (100)	60 (16.67) (100)	55 (15.28) (100)	360 (100) (100)
Chi-Square	$\chi^2 = 57.928^{**}$			

Source: Field Survey

Note: ****Significant at 0.01 level**

Table 1 shows that majority of the 315 sample respondent handloom weavers (87.50 per cent) were facing production problems and 45 sample respondent handloom weavers (12.50 per cent) responded that they were not facing production problems in Rayalaseema region.

Majority of the 236 sample respondent handloom weavers in Annamayya district (96.33 per cent), followed by Tirupati district (74.55 per cent) and Chittoor district (63.33 per cent) were facing production problems and the least number of sample respondent handloom weavers in Chittoor district (36.67 per cent), Tirupati district (25.45 per cent) and Annamayya district (3.67 per cent) said that they were not facing any production problems.

The calculated value of χ^2 -test statistic (57.928) is much higher than its critical value (9.210). Hence, the null hypothesis may be rejected at 1% level of significance. It can be inferred that there is a significant relationship between whether they are facing production problems or not of sample respondent handloom weavers of Annamayya, Chittoor and Tirupati districts in Rayalaseema region.

Table 2: Production problems of sample respondent handloom weavers in Rayalaseema region

Production Problems	Name of the District			Total
	Annamayya	Chittoor	Tirupati	
Scarcity of Raw Materials	195(82.28) (82.63)	18(7.59) (47.37)	24(10.13) (58.54)	237(100) (75.24)
High Cost	20(51.28) (8.47)	10(25.64) (26.32)	09(23.08) (21.95)	39(100) (12.38)
Equipment Problems	12(52.17) (5.08)	06(26.09) (15.79)	05(21.74) (12.20)	23(100) (7.30)
Deficit of Power	09(56.25) (3.81)	04(25.00) (10.53)	03(18.75) (7.32)	16(100) (5.08)
Total	236(74.92) (100.00)	38(12.06) (100)	41(13.02) (100.00)	315(100) (100.00)
Chi-Square	$\chi^2 = 29.108^{**}$			

Source: Field Survey

Note: ****Significant at 0.01 level**

Table 2 reveals that majority of the 237 sample respondent handloom weavers in Rayalaseema region (75.24 per cent) said that the scarcity of raw materials were facing the major problem, followed by 39 sample respondent handloom weavers (12.38 per cent) who said that the problem for them in connection with the production was that the material cost was high, 23 sample respondent handloom weavers (7.30 per cent) were facing equipment problems

and 16 sample respondent handloom weavers (5.08 per cent) were facing a problem relating to deficiency of power.

195 out of 236, 24 out of 41 and 18 out of 38 sample respondent handloom weavers from Annamayya, Tirupati and Chittoor districts respectively responded that they had problem relating to production because of scarcity of raw materials and the least number of sample respondent handloom weavers 09 out 236, 04 out of 38 and 03 out of 41 in Annamayya, Chittoor and Tirupati districts respectively were facing problem relating to deficit of power.

The calculated value of χ^2 -test statistic (29.108) is much higher than its critical value (16.812). Hence, the null hypothesis may be rejected at 1% level of significance. It can be inferred that there is a significant relationship between the production problems of sample respondent handloom weavers of Annamayya, Chittoor and Tirupati districts in Rayalaseema region.

FINANCIAL PROBLEMS

The handloom industry is one such delicate organization, which has been totally a capital starved all the time. By and large, sound financial assistance from government alone could improve the competitive urge among handloom co-operatives. The Government of India and State Governments should provide financial assistance to handloom weavers, handloom weavers' co-operative societies for strengthening the share capital, improving the management of societies and modernization of looms. Even then, the co-operative societies could not strengthen their financial position because, they are not able to repay in time the loan received and hence the co-operative societies have to pay interest to the District Central Co-operative Banks. The sample respondent handloom weavers whether they are facing financial problems or not in Rayalaseema region is presented in table 3 hereunder;

Table 3: Sample respondent handloom weavers whether they are facing financial problems or not in Rayalaseema region

Sample respondent handloom weavers	Name of the District			Total
	Annamayya	Chittoor	Tirupati	
Yes	239(74.92) (97.55)	56(12.06) (93.33)	47(13.02) (85.45)	342(100) (95.00)
No	06 (33.33) (2.45)	04 (22.22) (6.67)	08 (44.45) (14.55)	18 (100) (5.00)
Total	245 (68.06) (100)	60 (16.67) (100)	55 (15.28) (100)	360 (100) (100)
Chi-Square	$\chi^2 = 14.258^{**}$			

Source: Field Survey

Note: **Significant at 0.01 level

Table 3 depicts that majority of the 342 sample respondent handloom weavers (95.00 per cent) were facing the financial problems and 18 sample respondent handloom weavers (5.00 per cent) opined that they were not facing financial problems in Rayalaseema region.

Majority of the 239 sample respondent handloom weavers in Annamayya district (97.55 per cent), followed by 56 sample respondent handloom weavers (93.33 per cent) in Chittoor district and 47 sample respondent handloom weavers (85.45 per cent) in Tirupati district opined that they were facing financial problems and the least number of 08 sample respondent handloom weavers in Tirupati district (14.55 per cent), 06 sample respondent handloom weavers (2.45 per cent) in Annamayya district and 04 sample respondent handloom weavers (6.67 per cent) in Chittoor district opined that they were not facing any financial problems.

The calculated value of χ^2 -test statistic (14.258) is much higher than its critical value (9.210). Hence, the null hypothesis may be rejected at 1% level of significance. It can be inferred that there is a significant relationship between whether they are facing financial problems or not of sample respondent handloom weavers of Annamayya, Chittoor and Tirupati districts in Rayalaseema region.

Table 4: Sample respondent handloom weavers are facing financial problems in Rayalaseema region

Financial Problems	Name of the District			
	Annamayya	Chittoor	Tirupati	Total
High rate of interest	98 (75.38) (41.00)	20 (15.38) (35.71)	12 (9.23) (25.53)	130 (100) (38.01)
Too many formalities	37 (62.71) (15.48)	09 (15.25) (16.07)	13 (22.03) (27.66)	59 (100) (17.25)
Influence required	49 (67.12) (20.50)	17 (23.29) (30.36)	07 (9.59) (14.89)	73 (100) (21.35)
Security to be furnished	55 (68.75) (23.01)	10 (12.50) (17.86)	15 (18.75) (31.91)	80 (100) (23.39)
Total	239(74.92) (100)	56(12.06) (100)	47(13.02) (100)	342(100) (100)
Chi-Square	$\chi^2 = 11.332^@$			

Source: Field Survey

Note: @Not Significant

Table 4 shows that majority of the 130 sample respondent handloom weavers in Rayalaseema region (38.01 per cent) responded that they were facing financial problems because the financial institutions which accessible to them are charging abnormal rate of interest, followed by 80 sample respondent handloom weavers (23.39 per cent) said that they

could not furnish security to their bank officers to get loans from the banks which are within the vicinity of their residence and work place, 73 sample respondent handloom weavers (21.35 per cent) said that they have no access to people who can influence the officers concern in their respective banks to get loans for them and 59 sample respondent handloom weavers (17.25 per cent) were facing too many formalities in Rayalaseema region.

Majority of the 98 sample respondent handloom weavers in Annamayya district (41.00 per cent), followed by 20 sample respondent handloom weavers (35.71 per cent) in Chittoor district responded that they were facing charging abnormal rate of interest and 15 sample respondent handloom weavers in Tirupati district (31.91 per cent) said that they could furnish security to their bank officers to get loans from the banks which are within the vicinity of their residence and the least number of 07 sample respondent handloom weavers in Tirupati district (14.89 per cent) were facing influence required, 09 sample respondent handloom weavers (16.07 per cent) in Chittoor district and 37 sample respondent handloom weavers (15.48 per cent) in Chittoor district opined that they were facing too many formalities.

The calculated value of χ^2 -test statistic (11.332) is less than its critical value (12.592). Hence, the null hypothesis may be accepted at 5% level of significance. It can be inferred that there is no significant relationship between the financial problems of sample respondent handloom weavers of Annamayya, Chittoor and Tirupati districts in Rayalaseema region.

HEALTH PROBLEMS

Handloom weavers are facing major health problems such as eye sight weakness, back pain, knee pain and lungs problems. The sample respondent handloom weavers whether they are facing health problems or not in Rayalaseema region is presented in table 5 hereunder;

Table 5: Sample respondent handloom weavers whether they are facing health problems or not in Rayalaseema region

Sample respondent handloom weavers	Name of the District			
	Annamayya	Chittoor	Tirupati	Total
Yes	235 (72.31) (95.92)	50 (15.38) (83.33)	40 (12.31) (72.73)	325 (100) (90.28)
No	10 (28.57) (4.08)	10 (28.57) (16.67)	15 (42.86) (27.27)	35 (100) (9.72)
Total	245 (68.06) (100)	60 (16.67) (100)	55 (15.28) (100)	360 (100) (100)
Chi-Square	$\chi^2 = 31.480^{**}$			

Source: Field Survey

Note: ****Significant at 0.01 level**

Table 5 depicts that majority of the 325 sample respondent handloom weavers (90.28 per cent) were facing health problems and 35 sample respondent handloom weavers (9.72 per cent) were not facing health problems in Rayalaseema region.

Majority of the 235 sample respondent handloom weavers in Annamayya district (95.92 per cent), followed by 50 sample respondent handloom weavers (83.33 per cent) in Chittoor district and 40 sample respondent handloom weavers (72.73 per cent) in Tirupati district opined that they were facing severe health problems and 15 sample respondent handloom weavers in Tirupati district (27.27 per cent), 10 sample respondent handloom weavers (16.67 per cent) in Chittoor district and Annamayya district (4.08 per cent) opined that they were not facing health problems.

The calculated value of χ^2 -test statistic (31.480) is much higher than its critical value (9.210). Hence, the null hypothesis may be rejected at 1% level of significance. It can be inferred that there is a significant relationship between whether they are facing health problems or not of sample respondent handloom weavers of Annamayya, Chittoor and Tirupati districts in Rayalaseema region.

Table 6: Sample respondent handloom weavers are facing health problems in Rayalaseema region

Health Problems	Name of the District			Total
	Annamayya	Chittoor	Tirupati	
Eye Sight	25 (65.79) (10.64)	06 (15.79) (12.00)	07 (18.42) (17.50)	38 (100) (11.69)
Back pain	105 (75.00) (44.68)	21 (15.00) (42.00)	14 (10.00) (35.00)	140 (100) (43.08)
Knee Pain	87 (75.65) (37.02)	15 (13.04) (30.00)	13(11.30) (18.92)	115 (100) (35.38)
Problems of lungs	18 (56.25) (7.66)	08 (25.00) (16.00)	06 (18.75) (15.00)	32 (100) (9.85)
Total	235 (72.31) (100)	50 (15.38) (100)	40 (12.31) (100)	325 (100) (100)
Chi-Square	$\chi^2 = 6.966@$			

Source: Field Survey

Note: **@Not Significant**

Table 6 portrays that majority of the 140 sample respondent handloom weavers (43.08 per cent) were suffering from back pain, followed by 115 sample respondent handloom weavers (35.38 per cent) were suffering from Knee pain, 38 sample respondent handloom weavers (11.69 per cent) were suffering from eye sight and 32 sample respondent handloom weavers (9.85 per cent) were suffering from lungs problems in Rayalaseema region.

In Annamayya district majority of the 105 sample respondent handloom weavers (44.68 per cent) said that they were suffering from Back pain and the least number of 18 sample respondent handloom weavers (7.66 per cent) were suffering from lungs decease. Majority of the 14 sample respondent handloom weavers in Tirupati district (35.00 per cent) said that they were suffering from back pain problem and the least number of 06 sample respondent handloom weavers (15.00 per cent) were suffering from lungs decease. In Chittoor district, majority of the 21 sample respondent handloom weavers (42.00 per cent) said that they were suffering from Back pain and the least number of 06 sample respondent handloom weavers (12.00 per cent) said that they were suffering from eye sight.

The calculated value of χ^2 -test statistic (6.966) is less than its critical value (12.592). Hence, the null hypothesis may be accepted at 5% level of significance. It can be inferred that there is no significant relationship between the health problems of sample respondent handloom weavers of Annamayya, Chittoor and Tirupati districts in Rayalaseema region.

LABOUR PROBLEMS

Handloom weavers are also facing labour problems viz., Scarcity of skilled labour, Demands High wages, No production and other problems. The sample respondent handloom weavers whether they are facing labour problems or not in Rayalaseema region is presented in table 7 as follows;

Table 7: Sample respondent handloom weavers whether they are facing labour problems or not in Rayalaseema region

Sample respondent handloom weavers	Name of the District			
	Annamayya	Chittoor	Tirupati	Total
Yes	233 (68.93) (95.10)	56 (16.57) (93.33)	49 (14.50) (89.09)	338 (100) (93.89)
No	12 (54.55) (4.90)	04 (18.18) (6.67)	06 (27.27) (10.91)	22 (100) (6.11)
Total	245 (68.06) (100)	60 (16.67) (100)	55 (15.28) (100)	360 (100) (100)
Chi-Square	$\chi^2 = 2.867^@$			

Source: Field Survey

Note: @Not Significant

Table 7 depicts that majority of the 338 sample respondent handloom weavers (93.89 per cent) were facing labour problems and 22 sample respondent handloom weavers (6.11 per cent) were not facing labour problems in Rayalaseema region.

Majority of the 233 sample respondent handloom weavers in Annamayya district (95.10 per cent) were facing labour problems and 12 sample respondent handloom weavers (4.90 per cent) were not facing labour problems. Majority of the 56 sample respondent handloom weavers in Chittoor district (93.33 per cent) were facing labour problems and only four sample respondent handloom weavers (6.67 per cent) were not facing labour problems. Majority of the 49 sample respondent handloom weavers (89.09 per cent) in Tirupati district were facing labour problems and only six sample respondent handloom weavers (10.91 per cent) were not facing any labour problems.

The calculated value of χ^2 -test statistic (2.867) is less than its critical value (5.991). Hence, the null hypothesis may be accepted at 5% level of significance. It can be inferred that there is no significant relationship between whether they are facing labour problems or not of sample respondent handloom weavers of Annamayya, Chittoor and Tirupati districts in Rayalaseema region.

Table 8: Sample respondent handloom weavers are facing labour problems in Rayalaseema region

Labour Problems	Name of the District			Total
	Annamayya	Chittoor	Tirupati	
Scarcity of skilled labour	26(51.06) (11.16)	15(21.28) (26.79)	13(27.66) (26.53)	54 (100.00) (15.98)
Demands High wages	173(81.40) (74.25)	23(9.05) (41.07)	29(9.55) (59.18)	225 (100.00) (66.57)
No production	28(61.76) (12.02)	11(17.65) (19.64)	04(20.59) (8.16)	43 (100.00) (12.72)
Others	06(65.00) (2.58)	07(20.00) (12.50)	03(15.00) (6.12)	16 (100.00) (4.73)
Total	233 (68.93) (100)	56 (16.57) (100)	49 (14.50) (100)	338 (100) (100)
Chi-Square	$\chi^2 = 31.460^{**}$			

Source: Field Survey

Note: ****Significant at 0.01 level**

Table 8 shows that majority of the 225 sample respondent handloom weavers in Rayalaseema region (66.57 per cent) responded that they were facing in demanded high wages, followed by 54 sample respondent handloom weavers (15.98 per cent) who said that the skilled labour were not available to them, 43 sample respondent handloom weavers (12.72 per cent) said that they did not undertake weaving activity for a few days in a year and 16 sample respondent handloom weavers (4.73 per cent) said that they had been facing other problems.

Majority of the 173 sample respondent handloom weavers in Annamayya district (74.25 per cent), followed by 23 sample respondent handloom weavers (41.07 Per cent) in Chittoor district and 29 sample respondent handloom weavers (59.18 per cent) in Tirupati district said that the labour they hired for their handloom weaving activity demanded for higher wages and the least number of 07 sample respondent handloom weavers (12.50 per cent) in Chittoor district, 06 sample respondent handloom weavers (6.12 per cent) in Annamayya district and 03 sample respondent handloom weavers (2.58 per cent) in Tirupati district have responded that they were facing other problems.

The calculated value of χ^2 -test statistic (31.460) is much higher than its critical value (16.812). Hence, the null hypothesis may be rejected at 1% level of significance. It can be inferred that there is a significant relationship between the labour problems of sample respondent handloom weavers of Annamayya, Chittoor and Tirupati districts in Rayalaseema region.

FINDINGS

- Majority of the 315 sample respondent handloom weavers (87.50 per cent) were facing production problems and 45 sample respondent handloom weavers (12.50 per cent) responded that they were not facing production problems in Rayalaseema region. Majority of the 236 sample respondent handloom weavers in Annamayya district (96.33 per cent) were facing production problems and the least number of sample respondent handloom weavers in Annamayya district (3.67 per cent) said that they were not facing any production problems.
- Majority of the 237 sample respondent handloom weavers (75.24 per cent) said that the scarcity of raw materials were the major problem and the least number of 16 sample respondent handloom weavers (5.08 per cent) were facing a problem relating to deficiency of power in Rayalaseema region. Majority of the 195 sample respondent handloom weavers in Annamayya district responded that they had problem relating to production because of scarcity of raw materials and the least number 03 of sample

respondent handloom weavers in Tirupati district were facing problem relating to deficit of power.

- Majority of the 342 sample respondent handloom weavers (95.00 per cent) opined that they were facing the financial problems and 18 sample respondent handloom weavers (5.00 per cent) were not facing financial problems in Rayalaseema region. Majority of the 239 sample respondent handloom weavers (97.55 per cent) were facing financial problems in Annamayya district and the least number of 04 sample respondent handloom weavers (6.67 per cent) were not facing any financial problems in Chittoor district.
- Majority of the 130 sample respondent handloom weavers (38.01 per cent) responded that they were facing financial problems and 59 sample respondent handloom weavers (17.25 per cent) opined that they were facing too many formalities in Rayalaseema region. Majority of the 98 sample respondent handloom weavers (41.00 per cent) responded that they were facing charging abnormal rate of interest in Annamayya district and the least number of 07 sample respondent handloom weavers (14.89 per cent) in Tirupati district opined that they were facing influence required.
- Majority of the 325 sample respondent handloom weavers (90.28 per cent) were facing health problems and 35 sample respondent handloom weavers (9.72 per cent) were not facing health problems in Rayalaseema region. Majority of the 235 sample respondent handloom weavers (95.92 per cent) opined that they were facing severe health problems in Annamayya district and the least number of 10 sample respondent handloom weavers (4.08 per cent) opined that they are not facing health problems in Annamayya district.
- Majority of the 140 sample respondent handloom weavers (43.08 per cent) were suffering from back pain and the least number of 32 sample respondent handloom weavers (9.85 per cent) were suffering from lungs problems in Rayalaseema region. Majority of the 105 sample respondent handloom weavers (44.68 per cent) said that they were suffering from back pain in Annamayya district and the least number of 06 sample respondent handloom weavers (12.00 per cent) said that they were suffering from eye sight in Chittoor district.
- Majority of the 338 sample respondent handloom weavers (93.89 per cent) were facing labour problems and 22 sample respondent handloom weavers (6.11 per cent) were not facing labour problems in Rayalaseema region. Majority of the 233 sample respondent handloom weavers (95.10 per cent) were facing labour problems in Annamayya district

and the least number only four sample respondent handloom weavers (6.67 per cent) were not facing any labour problems in Chittoor district.

- Majority of the 225 sample respondent handloom weavers (66.57 per cent) responded that they were facing in demanded high wages and the least number of 16 sample respondent handloom weavers (4.73 per cent) were facing other problems in Rayalaseema region. Majority of the 173 sample respondent handloom weavers (74.25 per cent) said that the labour they hired for their handloom weaving activity demanded for higher wages in Annamayya district and the least number of 03 sample respondent handloom weavers (6.12 per cent) have responded that they were facing other problems in Tirupati district.

SUGGESTIONS

- The Government of India has been introduced several welfare schemes to handloom weavers but, the benefits are not reached to appropriate person various steps to be taken for attractive benefits.
- The State government may allocate sufficient funds and to arrange a separate training agency in this regard. All the eligible handloom weavers should be sent to the training Programme. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct periodic training programmes regularly.
- Providing training programmes to the handloom weavers which is necessary in the development of new designs and methods of production to attract the consumer from textile cloth production, would prove helpful in resolving the crisis to a considerable extent.
- The majority handloom weavers are not aware of insurance schemes so that the State Government should take proper steps to bring them insurance coverage.
- Majority of the handloom weavers depend up on the banks for raising funds, bank should provide subsidies for the loan taken by handloom weavers.
- The handloom weavers can keep their consumers in touch by making 'what's app' and some other social media.
- The Central and State Government should also provide scholarships to the children of handloom weavers for imparting them good education.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that the handloom weavers of Rayalaseema region in Andhra Pradesh various problems are faced in respect of production, finance, health and labour problems. The weavers cannot sell their products directly to the consumers. Today's no modern marketing techniques especially e- marketing, are not adopted by them. The weavers can keep their consumers in touch by making 'whatsapp' and other social media. But, the handloom weavers do not have any ideas awareness towards these issue. They cannot face the heavy competition generated by the large-scale textile sector and even small power looms. However, the policy makers should realize the importance of handloom sector and allocate the more required funds to handloom weavers.

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